

Organizational Performance as A Mediator for The Variable Impact of Total Quality Management, Organizational Trust, and Esprit De Corps on The Quality of Higher Education

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to evaluate hypotheses and research models about the characteristics that effect organizational performance and higher education quality in Indonesia. This study used a sample size of 320 participants and generated up to 280 research respondents who completed online questionnaires. The findings indicate that Total Quality Management (TQM) plays a critical role in effecting organizational performance and effecting the higher education quality, particularly at Indonesian private universities. In this case, organizational performance acts as a mediator between TQM constructs and the higher education wuality at Indonesian private universities. Organizational performance has a beneficial effect on the quality of private university higher education in Indonesia, and organizational trust is a significant predictor of the private university education quality in Indonesia. The private university education in Indonesia can be judged by the performance of academic staff, administrative services, library services, curriculum structure, location, facilities, and job opportunities. Increasing commitment, competency, and information disclosure at each of Indonesia's private universities is critical for increasing education quality. The findings of this study demonstrate the existence of a model for effecting the higher education quality in Indonesia, identifying TQM, organizational performance, and organizational trust as the factors that determine the quality of higher education in Indonesia.

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1. Introduction

A critical organizational performance indicator enables academics and managers to examine particular activities taken by businesses and managers, how the business competes with its competitors, and how the business evolves and performs over time. Organizational performance is critical as a primary criterion for evaluation, as evidenced by its widespread use as a dependent construct. Organizational performance is important to modern organizations' survival and success due to market competition for consumers, inputs, and money. This construct has taken on a major role as a desired outcome in contemporary industrial activity. Organizational performance is a critical component in achieving organizational goals (Batilmurik et al., 2020).

The phenomenon of higher education quality improvement in Indonesia is an intriguing subject to examine in light of the disparities in educational quality between educational institutions, as evidenced by the quality results of the National Accreditation Agency for Higher Education, Ministry of Education and Culture (BAN PT) of assurance evaluation as an indicator of higher education quality in the form of a National Accreditation Score. Academics and consultants' increased focus on performance measurements reflects the growing pressure on higher education organizations to effect their performance (Maestro et al., 2021).

In the early 1980s, organizations began to implement TQM as a quality and productivity improvement program, resulting in increased organizational efficiency and the global success of Japanese corporations (Yusof & Aspinwall, 2000). Numerous recent studies confirm that the TQM strategy is equally applicable to the service industry (Huq & Stolen, 1998), although this sector still lacks TQM, and the majority of TQM research is undertaken in the manufacturing sector (Kumar et al., 2009). On the basis of these facts, this research will establish whether TQM is being implemented in one of Indonesia's largest service industries, namely education services, more specifically in the country's numerous private universities. Higher education institutions must maintain a high standard of education in order to sustain their position in the face of competition, as universities are educational service companies. TQM enables private universities to attract students in order to secure long-term funding. TQM also assists colleges in developing a high level of professionalism among educators and education workers through the different values, it encompasses (Zabadi, 2013).

In the context of educational issues, both those relating to lecturers' professional competence and their motivation for work. Lecturer performance, equity, relevance, productivity, effectiveness, and efficiency, as well as the quality of education, and thus the success of education, are heavily influenced by the performance of education actors, particularly lecturers, who serve as the spearhead of education and teaching management. Lecturers carry out their professional authority by assuming functional positions that must be founded on professional competence. Lecturers are expected to possess professional competence and be able to perform tasks within their areas of expertise.

The aim of this study is to evaluate hypotheses and research models about the characteristics that effect organizational performance and higher education quality in Indonesia. This research is descriptive in nature and tries to provide an outline of the variables' features. This research is confirmatory in nature since it was undertaken to ascertain whether the developed model may be used as a decision-making tool and to ascertain the relationship between variables in hypothesis testing.

2. Theoretical Review

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Organizational Performance

In general, organizational performance is defined as the actual output or organizational results in comparison to the expected output or goals and objectives (Seralurin et al., 2020). The level of organizational performance is determined by a variety of factors, including operational efficiency, mergers and acquisitions, degree of diversification, organizational structure, composition and style of the top management team, human resource management (HRM), and manipulation of disruptive political and/or social influences on market fit. According to King (2007), diverse interpretations of socially responsible behavior, international or cross-cultural expansion or adaptation initiatives, and other organizational and/or sectoral level phenomena all serve as predictors of organizational success.

To ensure this research focused and concentrated, the construct of organizational performance, specifically the performance of several private colleges in Indonesia, is measured exclusively through non-financial measures. The non-financial aspect, in particular, is based on a triadic set of theories and concepts proposed by (1) Aluko (2003) consisting of three dimensions including owners, employees, and customers and (2) Miller (2016) which consists of seven dimensions including effectiveness, productivity, quality, customer satisfaction, efficiency, innovation, and financial resilience. PTS as a higher education institution, in addition to trying to obtain financial benefits, also carries out a 'social function' in the context of the intellectual life of the nation and state.

Higher Education Quality

The Higher Education Quality Assurance System (SPMPT) is a systemic activity to improve the quality of higher education as a whole in a planned and sustainable manner (Tammubua & Pattiasina, 2019). The Higher Education Quality Assurance System (SPMPT) consists of SPMI and SPME. SPMI is a systemic activity of quality assurance of higher education by each university autonomously to control and improve the implementation of higher education in a planned and sustainable manner which is planned, implemented, controlled, and developed by PT. SPME is an assessment activity through accreditation to determine the feasibility and level of achievement of the quality of study programs and universities in Indonesia.

According to Tsinidou, Gerogiannis, and Fitsilis (2010), elements affecting the quality of higher education institutions in Greece include academic staff, administrative services, library services, curriculum structure, location, facilities, and career prospects. Cabral and Huet (2014) discovered that one of the elements affecting the quality of higher education in the United Kingdom is the quality of research undertaken by academics within the institution. The findings of Abidin's (2015) research at the State Islamic University (UIN) of Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang indicate that the curriculum, Teaching and Learning Activities (KBM), administrative services, facilities, and libraries all contribute to the university's excellence.

The Higher Education Quality Enhancement Project (HEQEP) will consist of four components including (1) promotion of academic innovation in teaching-learning and research through the Academic Innovation Fun (AIF) which allocates funds by competitive base to public and private universities; (2) institutional capacity building of the University Grants Commission (UGC) and universities; (3) increasing connectivity capacity for universities and research centers through the development of the Bangladesh Research and Education Network (BdREN); and (4) support for the operation of the project implementation unit. The University Grants Commission of Bangladesh is the project implementing agency. A HEQEP unit has been established at UGC for the implementation, management, and monitoring and evaluation of activities.

Total Quality Management

Total Quality Management (TQM) is one of the quality-oriented approaches implied by many organizations. TQM has attracted many scientists, due to the growing spread and acceptance of this concept in the business world. Over the past two decades, TQM has been one of the most popular and enduring management concepts (Rahman & Bullock, 2005, p. 73). Quality management is a way of planning, organizing, and directing that will facilitate and integrate the ability of all employees to continuously improve anything and everything in an organization to achieve perfection (Garvin, 1986). Moreover, Rahman and Bullock (2005) argue that TQM is a management approach to improve organizational performance that covers a variety of technical and behavioral topics. Based on some of the opinions above, it can be concluded that TQM is management that is applied to all aspects that exist within the company to gain competitive advantage by continuously improving every aspect of organizational culture that brings everyone in the organization to ensure and improve the quality of product processes, work environment, and work culture. Therefore, TQM can be viewed functionally as an integration of two basic functions, namely quality control and total quality management.

Organizational Trust

Trust in organizations is frequently related with increased economic performance and achievement of organizational goals. In the twenty-first century, trust is vital to organizational excellence (Shockley-Zalabak, Morreale & Hackman, 2010). Numerous research conducted across diverse cultures and professions argue that trust is critical for successful collaboration and organizational effectiveness (Paliszkievicz, 2011). Nonprofits and businesses that have a high trust profile achieve more success. On the other hand, distrust results in massive losses for businesses (Braun, 1997). The term "organizational trust" in this study refers to the trust developed inside a variety of private institutions in Indonesia.

Mayer et al. (1995; 2001; 2005) describe trust as "the desire to be vulnerable to another party when that party is uncontrollable or monitorable." Another definition of trust is "a person's expectations, assumptions, or ideas about the likelihood that other people's future actions would be good, advantageous, or at the very least not damaging to one's interests" (Robinson, 1996).

Esprit de Corps

Esprit de corps is acknowledged as a factor in team involvement and as a primary factor in team strength (Qureshi & Hamid, 2017, p. 238). It is a phenomenon that exists in its own category and is based on the perception and assumption that employees are fully aware of the group. This is referred to as the organization's team spirit and the degree to which its personnel care about one another's concerns. Employees who have a deep connection to the organization's numerous activities and issues perform better when they have esprit de corps. This construct is developed in organizations on the idea that a team is made up of individuals who collectively rely on one another to work together to accomplish a common goal that serves as the team's driving force. This is a collective cohesiveness, organizational identification (recognition), and esprit de corps phenomena. Even in the midst of opposition, esprit de corps demonstrates a strong desire to achieve common goals." (Halepota & Irani, 2010).

Esprit de corps is a valuable attribute among members of an organization who lack official authority over one another (Homburg et al., 2003). Esprit de corps shows a high desire to realize organizational goals and improve performance with teamwork and support each other” (Qureshi & Hamid, 2015). In practice, creative esprit de corps tends to evolve into autonomist esprit de corps, autonomist esprit de corps tends to turn into conformative esprit de corps, and universal esprit de corps always oscillates between the tendency to change to conformative esprit de corps and creative esprit de corps (De Miranda et al., 2015; 2016).

2. Materials and Methods

This research is confirmatory because this research was conducted to determine whether the developed model can be accepted as a tool for decision making and to determine the relationship between variables in hypothesis testing. This research was undertaken in Indonesian private universities. Purposive sampling was employed to determine the group of teaching staff at private universities (PTS) with at least two years of experience. Respondents who work in private institutions are randomly selected from each region. Private universities with accreditation A are included in the sample. If no private universities with accreditation A are available, those with accreditation B are chosen. Universities are the ideal sort of private universities to sample. The data were analyzed using the SEM-LISREL 8.8 program, which is an analytical tool for conceptually describing the obtained results and comparing them to those of earlier investigations.

Research Hypothesis

H1: Total Quality Management (TQM) has an effect on the performance of private universities in Indonesia.

H2: Organizational trust affects the performance of private universities in Indonesia.

H3: Esprit de corps has an effect on the performance of private universities in Indonesia.

H4: Total Quality Management (TQM) affects the quality of education in private universities in Indonesia.

H5: Organizational trust affects the quality of private higher education in Indonesia.

H6: Esprit de corps affect the quality of education in private universities in Indonesia.

H7: Organizational performance is able to mediate the influence of Total Quality Management (TQM), Organizational Trust, Esprit De Corps on the education quality of private universities in Indonesia.

3. Results and Discussions

After conducting a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) on each variable, the structural model is analyzed in its entirety. Figure 1 illustrates the estimation results for the whole structural model study. It is shown as follows.

Figure 1. Full Model Estimation Results

The magnitude of the parameter values in the relationship between the existing latent variables and the magnitude of the loading factor values for each indication that constitutes the latent variable are shown in Figure 1. By examining the existing parameter values, it is clear that the relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables is a negative one in some cases and a positive one in others. Additionally, the chart depicts the magnitude of direct influence and the contribution of each intervening component. Overall, exogenous variables have a positive effect on endogenous variables, with the exception of TQM's effect on university performance; nevertheless, TQM has a favorable effect on the quality of private universities. The overall test results for the full model analysis are shown in Figure 2

Figure 2 Full Model Test Results

The results of the tests for the measurement model and the structural model are shown in Figure 2. All parameters were examined using t-test statistics; if the t-value obtained was greater than 1.96, the parameter was statistically significant; if the t-count value obtained was less than 1.96, the parameter was not statistically significant. As illustrated in Figure 2, all indicators that comprise the latent variable are significant, as the t-value is more than 1.96, however the test results for the structural model, i.e. the relationship between latent variables, are significant in some cases but not in others. The test results of each parameter of the structural model are shown in Table 1.

Table 1
Results of Testing the Relationship Between Latent Variables.

Endogenous Variables	Exogenous/ Endogenous Variables	Estimate	S.E.	t-Value	Des.	R ²
Private University Performance	<--- TQM	-0,046	0,12	-0,39	Not significant	
Private University Performance	<--- Organizational Trust	0,009	0,09	0,09	Not significant	0,17
Private University Performance	<--- Esprit de corps	0,45	0,10	4,34	Significant	
Private University Education Quality	<--- Private University Performance	0,18	0,06	3,09	Significant	
Private University Education Quality	<--- TQM	0,21	0,09	2,35	Significant	
Private University Education Quality	<--- Organizational Trust	0,13	0,07	1,79	Not significant	0,62
Private University Education Quality	<--- Esprit de corps	0,38	0,08	4,84	Significant	

Based on Table 1. it can be seen that of the 7 (seven) hypotheses proposed, there are 4 (four) hypotheses that are accepted (significant) and 3 (three) hypotheses are not significant.

Intervening Effect Analysis Results

The intervening variable is said to be a perfect mediator if, after adding the intervening variable, the exogenous variable's effect on the endogenous variable becomes unimportant, implying that the exogenous variable's direct effect is not significant but the indirect effect is considerable. While the intervening variable is designated as a partial mediator if the exogenous variable's effect on the endogenous variable remains significant after the intervening variable is included, the significant value decreases but does not reach zero (Baron & Kenny, 1986)

Figure 3 Full Structure Model

The mathematical equation of this research model is as follows.

$$\text{PERFORMANCE} = -0.046 \cdot \text{TQM} + 0.0087 \cdot \text{TRUST} + 0.45 \cdot \text{ESPRIT}, R^2=0.17$$

(0.12) (0.090) (0.10)
-0.39 0.096 4.34

$$\text{QUALITY} = 0.18 \cdot \text{PERFORMANCE} + 0.21 \cdot \text{TQM} + 0.13 \cdot \text{TRUST} + 0.38 \cdot \text{ESPRIT}, R^2=0.62$$

(0.057) (0.091) (0.070) (0.078)
3.09 2.35 1.79 4.84

The magnitude of the direct influence, indirect effect and total effect of each relationship variable is shown in Table 2.

Table 2
Direct and Indirect Effects of Each Relationship

No	Connection	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect by:	Total Effect
			PERFORMANCE	

1	TQM --> PERFORMANCE	-0.046 ^{ns)}		-0.05
2	TRUST --> PERFORMANCE	0.009 ^{ns)}		0.01
3	ESPRIT --> PERFORMANCE	0.45		0.45
4	TQM --> QUALITY	0.22	-0.01	0.21
5	TRUST--> QUALITY	0.13 ^{ns)}	0.00	0.13
6	ESPRIT --> QUALITY	0.38	0.08	0.46
7	PERFORMANCE --> QUALITY	0.18		0.18

Description: TQM = TQM

^{ns)} = Not Significant level 5%

TRUST = Organizational Trust

ESPRIT = Esprit de corps

PERFORMANCE = Private University Performance

QUALITY = Private University Education Quality

The extent of the direct and indirect influence is shown in Table 2. Additionally, the table displays the cumulative effect of each variable on the other variables. Because the empirical model developed in this study includes intervening factors, it is required to demonstrate the role of each intervening variable using Table 2.

The analysis of the SEM model yielded estimation and test findings for the direct and indirect effects of TQM on the quality of private higher education as measured by private university performance. The magnitude of TQM's direct effect on the quality of private education is 0.22, which is statistically significant. The indirect effect of TQM on the quality of private higher education is -0.01 via private university performance. As a result, private university performance is insufficient as an intervening variable in the link between TQM and private university education quality, as the direct effect exceeds the indirect effect.

The analysis of the SEM model yielded estimation and testing results for the direct and indirect effects of organizational trust on the quality of private higher education via private university performance. The size of Organizational Trust's direct influence on the quality of private higher education is 0.13, which is not statistically significant. The level of Organizational Trust's indirect effect on the quality of private university education via private university performance is 0.00. As a result, private university performance is insufficient as an intervening variable in the link between Organizational Trust and Private University Education Quality, as the direct effect outweighs the indirect effect.

The results of the SEM model analysis provided estimation and testing results for the direct and indirect effects of Esprit de corps on the quality of private higher education as measured by private university performance. The size of Esprit de corps's direct influence on the quality of private education is 0.38, which is significant. The indirect effect of Esprit de corps on the quality of private higher education is 0.08, which is considerable. As a result, private university performance is insufficient to explain the link between Esprit de corps and Private University Education Quality.

4. Conclusion

According to the findings of this study's research and discussion, TQM does not have a direct effect on the performance of private universities, but does have a direct and significant effect on the quality of private private education in Indonesia. Organizational trust has a negligible effect on the

performance and quality of private universities in Indonesia. This is because the organizational structure and educational policies are still largely shaped and controlled by the central government, and thus the trust is based on government policies rather than on the organization. Corpsesprit has a strong favorable influence on private university performance. This means that the more the Corps Esprit, the greater the private university performance. Because the quality of higher education is influenced by the performance of private institutions in Indonesia, TQM may potentially have an effect on education quality indirectly. Private university performance has a positive and significant effect on the quality of private universities in Indonesia and is a direct predictor of private university quality improvement in Indonesia. This indicates that if private universities improve their performance, the quality of private education in Indonesia improves as well. Esprit de corps has a substantial positive effect on the quality of Indonesia's private universities. This suggests that a higher Esprit de corps indicates a higher private university quality. private university performance is insufficient as an intervening variable in the link between TQM and Private University Education Quality because the direct effect outweighs the indirect effect. Private university performance is insufficient as an intervening variable in the association between Organizational Trust and private university Education Quality because its direct effect is greater than its indirect effect. private university performance is insufficient as an intervening variable in the link between Esprit de corps and the quality of private university education.

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